

IMPACT OF THE MOTION OF A SHIP'S HF RECEIVER ON THE SPECTRAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THE IONOSPHERIC SIGNAL

S.B. Kashcheyev¹, A.V. Zalizovski^{1,2,3}, O.V. Budanov¹, O.V. Bogomaz^{2,4}, A.I. Reznychenko^{1,3}

¹*Institute of Radio Astronomy of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine, Kharkiv, Ukraine; 19kasb50@gmail.com;*

²*State Institution National Antarctic Scientific Center, Ministry of Educ. and Science of Ukraine, Kyiv, Ukraine;*

³*Space Research Centre of Polish Academy of Sciences, Warsaw, Poland;*

⁴*Institute of Ionosphere, National Technical University "Kharkiv Polytechnic Institute", Kharkiv, Ukraine*

Studying near-Earth space conditions (or space weather) is gaining great practical importance due to the active use of geospaces. Such studies are currently conducted using various contact and remote methods. In any case, electromagnetic signals propagate along ground-space paths through the heterogeneous and non-stationary ionosphere. Conditions of the ionosphere significantly affect the characteristics of electromagnetic signals, i.e., the quality of communication, the results of remote sounding, radio astronomy observations, etc.

To improve the quality of space weather analysis and forecasting it is necessary to increase the amount of primary data on geospace conditions. Networks of geophysical stations for various purposes are constantly operating on the continents, providing permanent information on space weather. But, such measurements are practically absent over the oceans. Thanks to Ukraine's acquisition of the research vessel *Noosfera*, it became possible to conduct a wide variety of radio measurements during long transoceanic crossings as well as in the vicinity of the coast of Antarctica. Part of such measurements is the study of the spectral characteristics of HF signals propagating along ionospheric radio paths of various lengths and directions.

The features of the motion of the ship's HF receiving facility in marine conditions (unsteady speed, course fluctuation, ship pitching) have a significant impact on the results of measurements of the spectral characteristics of ionospheric signals. The spectral composition of ship speed fluctuations was measured for different conditions. The dependence of speed instability and the spectrum of its fluctuations on the parameters of movement and weather was shown. The depth of ionospheric signal modulation due to ship speed fluctuations in specific conditions was estimated.

Additional spectral components of the ionospheric signal due to scattering from the waved sea surface were identified. Their frequency composition and dependence on the speed of the vessel were analyzed. Explanations for the broadening of the first-order Bragg maxima and the absence of maxima due to higher-order reflection from the sea surface are proposed. It has been experimentally shown that when the receiver is located on a moving vessel, the measured dynamic range of the ionospheric signal spectrum might decrease due to scattering from the waved sea. This effect must be taken into account when measuring the characteristics of HF sky waves onboard the vessel.